

PSSOH

**First national conference titled
Free software and open hardware applications
in Serbian *Primena slobodnog softvera i otvorenog hardvera* PSSOH
at the School of Electrical Engineering, University of Belgrade
Bulevar kralja Aleksandra 73, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia**

With great pleasure, we invite you to attend the first national PSSOH conference with international presence titled Free software and open hardware applications organized by the School of Electrical Engineering, University of Belgrade.

Main PSSOH topics:

- free software (FS) applications
- open hardware (OH) applications
- role and representation of women in FS and OH

Conference encompasses one-day invited talks.
PSSOH will be held at the main building of the School of Electrical Engineering, University of Belgrade in the room 61 (ground floor).

Save the date: October 13th 2018!

Our entrance is free and our doors are open!

See you in October!

e-mail: pssoh@etf.bg.ac.rs
website: pssoh.etf.bg.ac.rs
Twitter: [@pssoh_etf](https://twitter.com/pssoh_etf)
GitHub: [pssoh](https://github.com/pssoh)